

Exploring New Ways to Predict Angling Pressure and Catch Rates For Canadian Waters

Greetings Anglers!

The [University of Alberta](#) is working with [Angler's Atlas](#) to determine if angler survey information can be used to develop models that predict angling pressure and catch rates at water bodies across Canada. As an angler, you are invited to participate in this research study. You can make a substantial contribution to the development of these prediction models by telling us in this survey which factors influence your freshwater fishing activity. The research project aims to help fisheries biologists better manage freshwater fisheries for conservation and fishing enjoyment.

Chance to win - To make your participation worthwhile for you, we will be giving away **three \$100 gift cards to Canadian Tire** through a random draw (1 in 333 chance to win). For participation please indicate your email address in a separate form after completion of the survey.

Participation - If you wish to participate in this study, please complete the attached survey and press the "submit" button. The survey should take you approximately **10 minutes** to complete. You do not have to answer any questions that you do not want to answer. Should you choose to withdraw midway through the electronic survey simply close the link and no responses will be included. Given the anonymous nature of the survey, once you have submitted your responses it will no longer be possible to withdraw them from the study. Completion and submission of the survey mean your consent to participate. We would appreciate receiving your answers **before Thursday, August 31**. We will send you a notice of reminder regardless if you have already participated.

Confidentiality - The information that you will share will remain strictly confidential and will be used solely for the purposes of this research. All data from this survey, from the Angler's Atlas website and from the mobile app MyCatch will be anonymized, and only aggregated water body level data will be used (so **Secret Spots Stay Secret**). Only the research team and Angler's Atlas will have access to your answers. Your answers to open-ended questions may be used verbatim in presentations and publications but neither you (nor your organization) will be identified.

Project information - To learn more about this project, click [here](#). This research project is being led by [Julia Schmid](#) (University of Alberta), under the direction of [Mark Lewis](#) (University of Alberta/University of Victoria). If you have any questions or require more information about the study itself, please reach out to Sean Simmons (President, Angler's Atlas and MyCatch,

sean@anglersatlas.com or 250-613-7727,) or Julia Schmid (Postdoc, University of Alberta, jschmid@ualberta.ca). The survey is part of a larger research study "Assessing angler behaviour and fisheries using citizen science". The results of the research study will be published on the Angler's Atlas website.

The plan for this study has been reviewed by a Research Ethics Board at the University of Alberta (Ethics ID Pro00102610). If you have any questions regarding your rights as a research participant or how the research is being conducted you may contact the Research Ethics Office at 780-492-2615. Please keep this form for your records.

Thank you in advance for your valuable input.

PART 1: TELL US ABOUT YOUR FRESHWATER FISHING

This section will help us understand the primary motivations around your fishing preferences. Please note that the questions refer only to fishing in **freshwater**.

1. How far do you typically travel to go fishing?

Check all that apply.

- Less than 20 km
- 20 to 50 km
- 50 to 100 km
- 100 to 200 km
- More than 200 km

2. Over the past five years, how many short fishing trips did you go on each year?
(i.e., less than 100 km)

3. Over the past five years, how many long fishing trips did you go on each year?
(i.e., more than 100 km)

4. Does the distance you have to travel influence your choice of the water body? And if so, why?

5. What are your primary reasons you go fishing? (Please select a maximum of three answers)

Check all that apply.

- Relaxation
- Enjoyment
- Food
- Sport
- Competition (e.g., tournaments)
- Social experience (family / friends)
- Being outside
- Other: _____

6. What kind of water body do you prefer for freshwater fishing?

Mark only one oval.

- Big lake (i.e., tbd: specify surface area here)
- Small lake (i.e., tbd: specify surface area here)
- River
- Not important

7. Why do you prefer this kind of water body?

8. Do you prefer busy or quiet places to fish?

Mark only one oval.

- Busy places
- Quiet places
- Not important

9. Do you usually fish from the shore or a boat?

Mark only one oval.

- Shore
- Boat
- I do both.

10. Why do you prefer to fish from the shore or the boat?

11. Do fishing regulations (like fish size limits, bag size limits) influence your choice of water body?

Mark only one oval.

- I don't care about regulations
- I prefer water bodies with restrictions in fish size and bag size
- I prefer water bodies with restrictions in fish size
- I prefer water bodies with restrictions in bag size
- I prefer water bodies without any restrictions
- Other: _____

12. Is there anything else that influences the choice of the water body you fish?

13. Do you also go fishing in the ocean?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, I mainly fish in the ocean.
- Yes, but I prefer freshwater fishing.
- No.

14. How will these factors influence your fishing?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Usually cancel fishing	Might cancel fishing	Doesn't matter	Might go fishing	Usually going fishing
Hot weather	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Rainy weather	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Windy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Calm weather	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cold weather	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Low Air Pressure (Cloudy)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

15. Is there anything else about the weather that would affect your decision to go fishing or cancel a fishing trip?

16. What do you find Angler's Atlas helpful for?

Check all that apply.

- Maps on waterbodies
- Fish species in waterbodies
- Fishing regulations
- MyCatch fishing log book
- MyCatch fishing events
- Angler posts
- Other: _____

17. As a member of Angler's Atlas, what is the most useful information you receive?

18. Where do you usually record your fishing trip?

Mark only one oval.

- MyCatch App
- Angler's Atlas website
- None of these
- Other: _____

19. Do you record every fishing trip on the MyCatch app or the Angler's Atlas website?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- More than 50%
- Less than 50%
- No trips at all
- Only successful trips (= trips with catches)

20. Did Covid-19 affect your fishing activity?

Mark only one oval.

- I went fishing more often
- Didn't change
- I went fishing less often
- Other: _____

21. Did Covid-19 affect the distances you traveled to go fishing?

Mark only one oval.

- I went fishing closer to home
- Didn't change
- I went fishing further from home
- Other: _____

22. Is there anything else you would like to share with us regarding your ability to go fishing, or things that prevent you from fishing more and should change?

PART 2: TELL US ABOUT YOURSELF

This section will help us understand how fishing fits into your broader life.

23. How old are you?

Mark only one oval.

Under 16

16 to 25

26 to 35

36 to 45

46-55

56-65

66-75

Over 75

24. What is your gender?

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

25. What is your marital status?

Mark only one oval.

- Never married
- Married
- Divorced / separated
- Widowed
- Other: _____

26. What is your total combined family income for the past 12 months?

Mark only one oval.

- Under \$30,000
- \$30,000 - \$60,000
- \$60,000 to \$100,000
- \$100,000 to \$150,000
- Over \$150,000
- Choose not answer

27. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

Mark only one oval.

- 12th grade or less
- High school graduate
- Some college / Technical training
- College graduate
- University graduate
- Post graduate degree (Masters or Doctorate)

28. How many people live in your household, including yourself?

29. What is your employment status?

Mark only one oval.

- Employed full time
- Employed part time
- Unemployed
- Retired
- Other: _____

30. Do you own or have easy access to a vehicle?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes

31. Do you own or have easy access to a boat?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Sometimes

32. How many years have you been fishing?

33. How would you classify your fishing skills?

Mark only one oval.

Beginner

Intermediate

Expert

34. In which province do you fish the most?

Mark only one oval.

- Alberta
- British Columbia
- Manitoba
- New Brunswick
- Newfoundland and Labrador
- Nova Scotia
- Ontario
- Prince Edward Island
- Quebec
- Saskatchewan
- The Territories
- Other: _____

35. What is your postal code?

36. Is there anything else you can share that would help us understand the factors the influence your fishing activity?

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